

ANALYSING GROUP DISPARITIES IN MEAN YEARS OF SCHOOLING ACROSS INDIAN STATES: EVIDENCE FROM THE NSS 79TH ROUND SURVEY

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Abstract: This article analyses group disparities in educational development measured by Mean Years of Schooling (MYS), using the 79th round survey data of the National Sample Survey Office (NSSO). The analysis reveals significant state-wise variations in MYS and group disparities, suggesting that higher inequality hampers overall improvements in MYS. Additionally, MYS is closely correlated with income levels across Indian states. Therefore, addressing educational divides, beginning with reducing group inequality in MYS, is crucial for bridging economic disparities among states.

Keywords: Educational development, Mean years of schooling, Group inequality, Gender inequality, Rural-urban inequality, Regional inequality

1. Introduction

Education as a fundamental capability attribute is widely regarded as a vital instrument in shaping the social and economic development of a nation (Hannum and Buchmann, 2005; Tilak, 2006). The role of education in enhancing individual earnings and promoting economic growth, as a form of human capital, has long been recognized by scholars such as Becker (1962), Mincer (1974), and Schultz (1963). The differences in educational development help to explain variations in living standards across countries (Mankiw et al., 1992). Education plays an instrumental role in expanding human capabilities, as emphasized by Sen (1999).

The concept of education is usually defined by the development of knowledge and understanding—whether acquired through formal learning institutions or other means. Since much of the learning process occurs in educational institutions and can be easily measured in terms of schooling, formal education is typically used as the key indicator of educational development or attainment for policy-making and empirical analysis. The mean years of schooling is defined as the average number of years of education received by an individual. The mean years of schooling is a widely used educational indicator for cross-country comparisons (Barro and Lee, 2013; Ram, 1990;

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